

REAL-TIME UAV EARLY SMOKE DETECTION WITH A LIGHTWEIGHT, FEATURE-REFINED DETECTOR

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KEYWORDS

UAV smoke detection; lightweight YOLOv8; BiFormer attention; Ghost Shuffle Convolution; WIoU v3; real-time wildfire monitoring.

ABSTRACT

Wildfires are highly destructive, making early smoke detection crucial for rapid suppression. Existing UAV-based methods face challenges such as slow inference, limited accuracy, and weak sensitivity to small or diffuse smoke. This study introduces a lightweight YOLOv8-based detector enhanced with (1) Wise-IoU v3 for robust localization, (2) Ghost Shuffle Convolution for reduced computation and real-time efficiency, and (3) BiFormer attention to emphasize smoke cues while suppressing clutter. On a UAV smoke dataset, the model achieves 79.4% AP (+3.3 over baseline), with notable performance on small (71.3%) and large (92.6%) targets. The results highlight improved accuracy and efficiency, supporting practical real-time UAV-based wildfire monitoring.

1. Introduction

Wildfires are among the most destructive natural hazards, and their occurrence has intensified due to global warming, prolonged droughts, and El Niño events [1–3]. Since smoke often precedes open flames, its early detection provides a critical window for rapid suppression and damage mitigation [4,5].

Traditional monitoring strategies, such as watchtowers, patrols, and fixed sensors, offer limited coverage and high operating costs [6,7]. Satellite imagery extends observation but suffers from coarse resolution, revisit delays, and weather interference [8]. Vision-based methods with handcrafted features and classical classifiers (e.g., SVM, HMM) [9,10] are lightweight but prone to false alarms under clouds, haze, or domain shifts.

Deep learning has improved detection accuracy using CNN- and transformer-based models [11–14]. Yet, detecting small-scale, low-contrast smoke remains challenging, especially on resource-constrained UAVs. UAVs are promising due to their agile, low-altitude

surveillance and real-time communication capabilities [15,16], but onboard detectors must balance accuracy and efficiency.

In this work, we propose a real-time, lightweight, and feature-refined YOLOv8-based detector for UAV smoke imagery. Our main contributions are:

1. A lightweight detector optimized for real-time UAV smoke detection.
2. Integration of Wise-IoU v3 for precise localization.
3. BiFormer attention for better smoke-background discrimination.
4. Ghost Shuffle Convolution (GSConv) for efficient multi-scale feature fusion.
5. Comprehensive evaluation against YOLO variants and conventional baselines, showing consistent gains.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews related work, Section 3 introduces the dataset and architecture, Section 4 presents experiments and ablations, and Section 5 provides limitations and concluding remarks.

2. Related Work

2.1. Sensor vs. Vision-Based Approaches

Wildfire detection methods generally fall into sensor-based and vision-based categories. Sensor networks (e.g., fixed detectors, thermal sensors) provide early cues but suffer from sparse coverage and high maintenance costs in large-scale deployments. Vision-based strategies are more scalable and can be divided into (i) handcrafted feature pipelines and (ii) deep learning models.

2.2. Classical Vision Methods

Early vision-based systems relied on handcrafted features—color, texture, motion, or shape—combined with traditional classifiers such as SVM or HMM [6–9]. While fast, they require manual tuning, degrade under illumination/weather shifts, and often confuse smoke with clouds or fog, limiting scalability and robustness.

2.3. Deep Learning Approaches

Deep neural networks, particularly CNN-based detectors and YOLO variants, have improved robustness and precision by reducing manual feature design [10–13]. Transfer learning on large backbones and specialized loss functions further reduced false alarms. However, detecting small, diffuse smoke at early stages remains difficult, and many models demand heavy computation, making UAV deployment challenging.

2.4. UAV-Centric Detection

UAVs provide agile, low-altitude sensing and high-resolution imagery [14,15]. Yet, real-time detection onboard faces domain shifts (altitude, viewpoint, weather), distractors (clouds, haze), and resource constraints. Thus, UAV-compatible detectors must be both accurate and lightweight.

2.5. Lightweight and Attention Mechanisms

Recent studies highlight three promising directions:

- **Lightweight convolutions** (e.g., GSConv) to reduce FLOPs while maintaining feature fusion efficiency [16].
- **Attention mechanisms** (e.g., BiFormer) to enhance saliency of smoke in cluttered backgrounds [17].
- **Robust localization losses** (e.g., WIoU v3) to stabilize small/diffuse target detection [18].

Classical methods are efficient but brittle, while deep models improve accuracy yet often neglect UAV-specific constraints. Although YOLO-based detectors provide strong baselines, challenges remain in jointly addressing small-scale smoke detection, real-time edge deployment, and robustness under clutter. To bridge this gap, our work integrates BiFormer attention, GSConv, and WIoU v3 into a YOLOv8 framework, achieving improved accuracy and efficiency for UAV-based early smoke detection.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1. Overview of UAV-Assisted Early Smoke Detection

We propose a **real-time, UAV-assisted pipeline** for early wildfire smoke detection, built on a lightweight, feature-optimized YOLOv8 framework. The overall workflow is illustrated in **Figure 1**, where UAV imagery sequentially undergoes preprocessing, feature extraction, multi-scale fusion, detection, and post-processing.

Figure 1. Overview of the proposed wildfire smoke detection system based on UAV images

Preprocessing. Inputs are standardized (resize, normalization, optional dehazing) to ensure consistent feature quality.

Feature Extraction. A YOLOv8 backbone enhanced with BiFormer attention [17] emphasizes smoke-salient cues in cluttered forest scenes.

Multi-Scale Fusion. Standard convolutions in the neck are replaced with GSConv [16], reducing FLOPs while preserving fine-scale details necessary for detecting early, diffuse smoke plumes.

Detection Head. The module incorporates WIoU v3 [18], which stabilizes localization of small and low-contrast smoke targets.

Post-Processing. Predictions are refined with non-maximum suppression (NMS) and confidence thresholds. For UAV deployment, detections are time-stamped and optionally geo-referenced from telemetry data, enabling integration with fire response systems. Temporal smoothing is applied for video streams to suppress flickering. The detailed schematic is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Overview of the proposed forest fire smoke detection system based on UAV images

3.2. Original YOLOv8

Overview. Released by Ultralytics in early 2023, YOLOv8 advances detection accuracy and inference speed while maintaining a compact footprint. Its baseline architecture follows the standard backbone–neck–head design and serves as our reference detector [28]. The general structure is illustrated in Figure 3 (placed here, after this paragraph).

Backbone (modified CSPDarknet). Multi-scale features (B1–B5) are extracted through five downsampling stages. Unlike classical CSP blocks, YOLOv8 employs C2f modules, enhancing gradient flow and reducing redundancy. The core CBS (Conv–BN–SiLU) unit ensures stable training. At higher stages, SPPF replaces the original SPP, aggregating multi-receptive-field context with lower latency while retaining global cues [26,27].

Neck (PAN–FPN fusion). The PAN–FPN neck fuses fine-grained details (bottom-up) with semantic-rich features (top-down). Compared with YOLOv5/7, YOLOv8 removes the extra post-upsampling convolution in the PAN path, simplifying the structure while maintaining accuracy [48].

Head (decoupled, anchor-free). The decoupled detection head separates classification and box regression. Its anchor-free design improves efficiency by simplifying sample assignment. Loss functions include CIOU + DFL for regression and BCE for classification, while the Task-Aligned Assigner ensures stable optimization through dynamic label assignment [19–21].

Baseline Role. This canonical YOLOv8 configuration forms the foundation for our enhanced model, which incorporates BiFormer attention, GSConv, and WIoU v3 to achieve accurate and efficient early smoke detection in UAV imagery.

3.3. WIoUv3 Loss Function

Overview. For bounding box regression, we employ WIoUv3, a dynamic, non-monotonic focusing mechanism that extends beyond overlap, centroid distance, and aspect ratio. Unlike conventional IoU-based losses with fixed gradient emphasis, WIoUv3 dynamically reallocates gradients to down-weight outliers and prioritize medium-quality samples. This enhances both generalization and robustness in detection tasks.

Variants. Tong et al. [29] introduced three successive variants:

- **WIoUv1:** Uses distance as an attention metric and reduces penalties when predicted and ground-truth boxes are close, but struggles with stability.
- **WIoUv2:** Introduces a monotonic focusing coefficient (L_{IoU}) with normalization to improve convergence, yet remains less adaptive.
- **WIoUv3:** Incorporates an outlier factor β , yielding a non-monotonic focus coefficient r . This formulation reduces gradient allocation to both high- and low-quality anchors, allowing the model to concentrate on medium-quality

samples that drive stable training.

Advantages. WIoUv3 combines the benefits of EIoU and SIoU while adaptively re-weighting gradients. This results in more stable localization, especially for small, diffuse, and low-contrast smoke plumes - a key challenge in UAV-based early wildfire detection. By focusing on moderate anchors, the model avoids overfitting high-quality predictions and reduces noise from poor matches, ultimately achieving better robustness against cluttered forest backgrounds.

3.4. BiFormer Attention

Overview. UAV imagery often contains distracting background elements such as clouds, haze, or tree canopies, which can confuse detection models and lead to false alarms. To address this, we integrate the BiFormer attention module into the YOLOv8 backbone. This module selectively emphasizes smoke-relevant features while suppressing irrelevant background cues, thereby improving both detection accuracy and computational efficiency.

Dynamic Sparse Attention. Traditional attention is computationally heavy, making it unsuitable for UAVs with limited onboard resources. BiFormer overcomes this by using Bi-Level Routing Attention, which dynamically routes features to the most relevant regions. This reduces memory and computation costs while retaining global context, making it particularly effective for detecting small and diffuse smoke plumes in cluttered aerial scenes.

Block Design. The BiFormer block includes lightweight components such as DWConv (depthwise separable convolution) for efficient computation, LayerNorm (LN) for stable training, and an MLP for refining outputs. Within YOLOv8, the C2f block between stages B3 and B4 is replaced with BiFormer, enabling dynamic and efficient attention that strengthens smoke saliency while suppressing noise.

Figure 3. BiFormer attention mechanism: (a) Block architecture with DWConv, LN, Bi-Level Routing Attention, and MLP; (b) Bi-Level Routing Attention process showing how regions are dynamically selected and aggregated to highlight smoke-salient cues in UAV imagery.

3.5. Ghost Shuffle Convolution (GSConv)

Conventional CNNs rely on repeated convolution and downsampling, which compress spatial information into channel space but often lead to semantic loss. Standard convolution (SConv) preserves inter-channel relationships but increases parameters and slows inference. Depthwise separable convolution (DWConv) reduces complexity by factorizing operations, yet breaks inter-channel dependencies, which can lower accuracy.

GSConv [31] combines the advantages of both. It applies SConv and DWConv in tandem, retaining inter-channel dependencies while remaining computationally efficient. The outputs are then merged and shuffled, enhancing non-linear representations (Figure 6). This design improves the model's ability to capture the irregular shapes, dispersion patterns, and deformations of wildfire smoke under diverse environmental conditions.

Unlike conventional convolutions, GSConv efficiently balances **accuracy and speed**, making it well suited for real-time UAV deployment. However, applying GSConv across all stages would significantly increase computational load. Instead, we strategically employ it at a critical stage in YOLOv8 where most smoke-related features are extracted. This replacement reduces parameters and FLOPs while preserving representational power. The successive GSConv-shuffle operations enable efficient multi-channel feature fusion, closely approximating standard convolution performance but at much lower cost—allowing faster and more robust UAV-

based smoke detection.

Figure 4. Architecture of the GSConv module, which combines standard convolution, depthwise convolution, and channel shuffle to balance accuracy and efficiency.

3.6. Forest Fire Smoke Dataset Collection

A well-prepared dataset is essential for reliable deep learning-based smoke detection. The performance of detection models depends directly on the quality, diversity, and representativeness of training and testing images. However, existing open-access wildfire smoke

datasets [10,52,53] show notable limitations, particularly for UAV imagery.

To address these gaps, we curated a composite dataset consisting of:

- **Forest fire smoke images** from prior studies [10,22,23];
- **Non-wildfire wildland scenes** [54] to provide negative samples;
- **Supplementary UAV aerial imagery** from recordings and web sources, capturing wildfire events across varied environments.

The dataset primarily consists of aerial forest photographs, with original resolutions ranging from 2048×3072 to 512×512 pixels. All images were resized to 640×640 for YOLOv8 training. After manual cleaning and balancing, we obtained 3200 smoke images and 2800 non-smoke images.

Table 1.

Summary of the forest fire smoke dataset and its sources.

Dataset	Smoke Images	Non-Smoke Images	Total
Google	300	150	450
Kaggle	2500	2400	4900
Flickr	100	100	200
Bing	300	150	450
Total	3200	2800	6000

This dataset reflects diverse smoke appearances, densities, and scales, including small diffuse plumes and large dense clouds. Such diversity strengthens generalization in cluttered forest scenes and better represents real UAV monitoring conditions. Representative samples are shown in **Figure 5**.

Figure 5. Representative samples from the wildfire smoke dataset: (a) small concentrated plumes with fading edges; (b) medium- and

large-scale smoke; (c) non-smoke forest scenes under varying weather (cloudy, sunny); (d) low-density smoke with weak edges, textures, and color—challenging for detection.

The dataset also addresses common challenges such as class imbalance, overfitting, and limited samples by applying data augmentation. Following prior studies [55–58], we used geometric transformations, including horizontal flips and counterclockwise rotations (60° and 120°). Non-smoke images of similar environments (mountains, fog, clouds) were included to reduce false positives.

In total, the dataset comprised 6000 original images (4800 for training, 1200 for testing). After augmentation, the training set expanded to 30,000

images, yielding a more balanced and robust dataset for UAV-based smoke detection.

Table 2.

Dataset augmentation strategy and statistics.

Category	Training Images (Original)	Training Images (Rotated)	Training Images (Flipped)	Testing Images (Original)	Total
Smoke images	2600	5200	7800	650	16,250
Non-smoke images	2200	4400	6600	550	13,750
Total	4800	9600	14,400	1200	30,000

4. Experimental Results

This section presents the hyperparameter settings, dataset configuration, and validation strategy used to evaluate the proposed YOLOv8-based wildfire smoke detector. All experiments

were conducted under consistent hardware conditions on a self-assembled workstation equipped with an NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1080 Ti GPU, 32 GB RAM, and a 9-core Intel CPU (4.9 GHz). The complete specifications are listed in **Table 3.**

Table 3.

Specifications of the hardware and software environment.

Item	Specification
GPU	2 × GeForce GTX 1080
CPU	Intel Core i9 Gen i7-9700K (4.90 GHz)
RAM	DDR4 32 GB (2 × 16 GB)
Motherboard	ASUS PRIME Z390-A STCOM
Operating System	Ubuntu Desktop 18.04 LTS
Storage	SSD: 512 GB + HDD: 4 TB (2 TB × 2)

The input images were drawn from the curated wildfire smoke dataset (Section 3.6) and uniformly resized to **640 × 640 pixels**. Model

training and evaluation followed standard YOLOv8 procedures, with hyperparameters summarized in **Table 4.**

Table 4.

Hyperparameter configuration for training the wildfire smoke detection model.

Epoch	200	The model goes through the entire dataset 200 times (more epochs → more learning, but also higher risk of overfitting).
Image size	640 × 640	Each image is resized to 640×640 pixels (larger size → more detail, but requires more computation).
Batch size	32	The model processes 32 samples at a time (larger batch → faster training, smaller batch → better generalization).
Learning rate	0.001	Step size for gradient descent (0.001 is a common, stable value for training).

Our evaluation framework included:

- **Baseline performance analysis** of YOLOv8;
- **Impact assessment** of the proposed architectural modifications;
- **Comparative study** with state-of-the-art detectors;
- **Ablation experiments** to isolate contributions of each component;
- **Visualization results** to qualitatively validate predictions.

This comprehensive setup ensured a rigorous assessment of the model's robustness and effectiveness in real-time UAV-based wildfire smoke detection.

4.1. Evaluation Metrics

The effectiveness of the proposed detector was quantitatively evaluated using the Microsoft COCO benchmark metrics [5,9,12,58–60]. Key indicators include:

- **Precision (P):** proportion of correctly detected smoke instances among all predicted positives, reflecting reliability in avoiding false alarms.
- **Recall (R):** ratio of correctly detected smoke instances to all ground-truth instances, measuring sensitivity to critical events.

An ideal detector achieves $P = 1$, $R = 1$, and a **false-negative rate of 0**. In this study, precision and recall were computed through pixel-level comparisons with annotated ground truths.

Table 5.

Microsoft COCO benchmarks for object detection methods.

Metric	Definition	Meaning
APS	AP for small objects (area < 32 ² pixels)	Evaluates performance on small-scale targets.
APM	AP for medium objects (32 ² < area < 96 ² pixels)	Performance on mid-sized targets.
APL	AP for large objects (area > 96 ² pixels)	Performance on large-scale targets.

In addition to P and R, we report **Average Precision (AP)** across small (APS), medium (APM), and large (APL) objects, following the COCO definitions. Detection speed was measured in **frames per second (FPS)**, while computational complexity was assessed via **floating-point operations (FLOPs)** to estimate resource demand.

Our enhanced YOLOv8-based detector achieved strong performance across multiple benchmarks, notably **APS = 78.5%** for small smoke plumes and **APL = 92.6%** for large-scale smoke. These results highlight robustness across varying smoke scales, a critical factor in UAV-

based wildfire monitoring.

We further compared the proposed model with both **multi-stage** and **single-stage detectors**:

- **Multi-stage models** such as Mask R-CNN and Cascade R-CNN demonstrated competitive AP50 scores (77.6% and 80.4%), though overall performance lagged behind our approach.
- **Single-stage models** such as YOLOv7 and YOLOv8 (baseline) performed well (AP = 75.2% and 76.1%, respectively), but the proposed method achieved higher AP while maintaining real-time inference speeds.

Table 6.

Comparison between the proposed method and multi-stage object detectors.

Model	AP	AP50	AP75	APS	APM	APL	FPS
MegDet [61]	64.2	73.1	67.2	54.8	63.5	78.1	–
Faster R-CNN [16]	65.7	72.6	67.3	55.7	64.4	76.3	–

Fast R-CNN [62]	63.5	70.3	64.4	53.1	62.3	75.2	–
Mask R-CNN [63]	69.3	77.6	73.0	60.5	68.2	81.0	–
Libra R-CNN [64]	54.4	65.5	61.2	45.2	53.6	70.4	–
DeNet [65]	57.1	66.3	60.5	47.3	58.4	72.4	–
Cascade R-CNN [66]	72.0	80.4	76.2	63.9	71.1	85.6	–
CoupleNet [67]	60.6	67.3	62.6	50.4	60.0	72.5	–
The Proposed	79.4	87.1	82.4	71.3	78.5	92.6	167

Table 7.

Comparison between the proposed method and single-stage object detectors.

Model	AP	AP50	AP75	APS	APM	APL	FPS
YOLOv5 [69]	72.3	80.0	74.2	64.6	71.4	85.4	160
YOLOv8 [28]	76.1	84.3	77.4	69.5	75.6	89.3	168
FSAF [71]	60.5	70.7	64.7	52.6	60.1	76.1	24
M2Det [72]	60.2	70.4	64.5	52.3	59.4	75.6	28
EfficientDet [73]	72.6	79.2	75.4	64.5	71.3	84.7	30
RefineDet [74]	70.0	77.3	72.7	61.7	68.5	83.3	63
SSD [75]	65.3	73.5	67.1	56.6	65.6	78.0	84
NAS-FPN [76]	63.2	73.0	67.3	55.1	62.7	77.1	22
DeepSmoke [77]	73.4	80.6	75.2	65.4	72.4	87.0	36
RFBNet [78]	64.2	70.1	65.0	53.2	61.0	74.8	27
RetinaNet [79]	67.0	74.7	69.1	58.5	65.1	70.5	69
The Proposed	79.4	87.1	82.4	71.3	78.5	92.6	167

Overall, the proposed YOLOv8-based wildfire smoke detector consistently outperformed state-of-the-art methods in both **accuracy** and **real-time performance (167 FPS)**, confirming its suitability for UAV-based early wildfire smoke detection.

4.2. Qualitative Evaluation

In addition to quantitative benchmarks, a qualitative evaluation was performed to further validate the effectiveness of the proposed wildfire smoke detector. Eight representative images from the test dataset were selected, including four with large-scale smoke plumes and four with small, spontaneous formations.

The enhanced YOLOv8 model demonstrated consistent detection performance across both categories. As illustrated in Figure 6, it reliably identifies smoke dispersing under diverse conditions and orientations, capturing both dense clouds and faint, diffuse traces. Unlike

conventional detectors that often miss subtle smoke patterns, the proposed model effectively detects even minor emissions, which are critical for early wildfire detection.

Figure 6b particularly highlights the challenge of small-scale smoke detection, where weak texture and low color contrast often lead to overlooked regions. To mitigate this, we adopted a feature fusion strategy inspired by prior research [9], in which low-level positional cues are integrated with high-level semantic features. This multi-scale fusion improves the model's ability to capture smoke signatures at different scales while reducing false positives.

Through this approach, the proposed model achieves strong generalization, effectively handling both large smoke plumes and subtle emissions. Such robustness is essential for UAV-based monitoring, where the timely identification of small smoke traces can significantly reduce response time and wildfire spread.

Figure 6. Qualitative examples of wildfire smoke detection: (a) large-scale smoke plumes; (b) small-scale smoke emissions. The proposed YOLOv8-based model accurately detects both categories, highlighting its robustness for UAV-based monitoring.

4.4. Ablation Study

To validate the contributions of individual components, we conducted ablation experiments on two aspects of the proposed YOLOv8 framework: (i) the choice of **bounding-box regression loss functions**, and (ii) the integration of **GSCnv** and **BiFormer** modules.

Bounding-Box Regression Loss

We first evaluated different IoU-based regression losses, including GIoU, DIoU, and CIoU, in comparison to the proposed **WIoUv3**. While GIoU extends IoU by penalizing non-overlapping boxes, it degenerates to IoU when one box is fully contained within another and often suffers instability with large directional disparities. DIoU incorporates a center-distance penalty for faster convergence but fails to capture fine-grained overlap information. CIoU further considers aspect ratios, though its reliance on relative ratios introduces uncertainty.

In contrast, **WIoUv3** stabilizes training by dynamically re-weighting penalties, enabling more precise localization of diffuse and irregular smoke plumes. As shown in **Table 8**, **WIoUv3** outperformed GIoU and DIoU across all COCO metrics, improving AP from 76.1% (baseline YOLOv8) to 76.9%. Furthermore, it reduced latency to 9 ms, underscoring its suitability for **real-time UAV deployment**.

Table 8.

Ablation results comparing different bounding-box regression losses in YOLOv8.

Model Variant	WIoUv3	GIoU	DIoU	AP	AP50	AP75	AP S	AP M	AP L	FP S	GFLOP S	Latency
Baseline YOLOv8	×	×	×	76.1	84.3	77.4	69.5	75.6	89.3	168	107.3	13 ms
YOLOv8 + WIoUv3	√	×	×	76.9	85.1	78.3	70.3	76.4	90.1	166	106.5	9 ms
YOLOv8 + GIoU	×	√	×	76.4	84.6	77.8	69.8	75.9	89.7	167	106.3	10 ms
YOLOv8 + DIoU	×	×	√	76.3	84.5	77.7	69.7	75.9	89.6	168	106.7	11 ms

Impact of GSCnv and BiFormer

We next examined the effect of lightweight convolutional and attention-enhancing modules. Four configurations were tested: baseline

YOLOv8 with WIoUv3, YOLOv8 + GSCnv, YOLOv8 + BiFormer, and YOLOv8 + GSCnv + BiFormer.

As summarized in **Table 9**, both modules independently improved detection accuracy, with

GSCnv yielding slightly higher AP than BiFormer. Their combined integration achieved the best performance, reaching **79.4% AP, 92.6% APL**, and maintaining a competitive inference speed of 167 FPS. This confirms that **GSCnv**

strengthens feature representation efficiency, while **BiFormer enhances multi-scale attention**, together producing a more robust detector for complex wildfire smoke scenarios.

Table 9.

Ablation results evaluating the impact of GSCnv and BiFormer modules on YOLOv8.

Model Variant	GSCnv	BiFormer	AP	AP50	AP75	APS	APM	APL	FPS	GFLOPS	Latency
Baseline (YOLOv8 + WIoUv3)	×	×	76.9	85.1	78.3	70.3	76.4	90.1	166	106.5	9 ms
+ GSCnv	√	×	78.3	86.3	80.5	70.9	77.6	91.5	168	106.7	9 ms
+ BiFormer	×	√	78.0	85.9	80.2	70.7	77.3	91.2	165	105.8	9 ms
+ GSCnv + BiFormer	√	√	79.4	87.1	82.4	71.3	78.5	92.6	167	103.5	8 ms

The ablation study demonstrates that while baseline YOLOv8 provides strong performance, its effectiveness in wildfire smoke detection is significantly enhanced when:

1. **WIoUv3** is used for bounding-box regression, yielding more stable localization.
2. **GSCnv + BiFormer** are integrated, improving generalization across varying smoke densities and scales.

These enhancements collectively enable the proposed model to achieve higher accuracy **without sacrificing real-time efficiency**, making it a practical solution for UAV-based wildfire monitoring.

5. Conclusions and Future Work

Wildfire smoke detection poses unique challenges compared to conventional computer vision tasks due to the irregular dynamics of smoke plumes and interference from environmental factors such as haze, fog, and cloud cover. In this study, we introduced an enhanced YOLOv8-based detection framework customized for complex forest environments, incorporating GSCnv, BiFormer, and WIoUv3 modules to improve robustness, accuracy, and efficiency.

Our model achieved AP of 79.4%, AP50 of 87.1%, and AP75 of 82.4%, representing

respective improvements of 3.3%, 2.8%, and 5.0% over the baseline YOLOv8. Furthermore, the system demonstrated strong scale adaptability, with APS of 71.3% for small plumes and APL of 92.6% for large smoke regions, surpassing both multi-stage detectors (e.g., Faster R-CNN, Cascade R-CNN) and single-stage detectors (e.g., YOLOv7, EfficientDet) in both detection accuracy and real-time inference speed.

Despite these promising results, several challenges remain. The model shows sensitivity to atmospheric interference such as haze and clouds, which can mimic smoke patterns and cause false alarms. Additionally, the current framework is optimized for daylight conditions, leaving nighttime or low-light smoke detection underexplored. To address these issues, future work will focus on integrating cloud-smoke discriminative modules, exploring thermal and low-light modalities, and reducing false positives through contextual priors such as fire-prone zones, temporal patterns, and meteorological data.

Finally, while the optimized YOLOv8 achieves real-time detection, deployment on resource-constrained edge devices requires further lightweight optimization. Future research will explore model compression, pruning, and knowledge distillation to adapt the framework for UAVs and IoT platforms without compromising performance. In parallel, expanding dataset diversity and incorporating multimodal

information, including satellite imagery and environmental data, will enhance the robustness and generalizability of the system.

In summary, the proposed YOLOv8 improvements advance the state of UAV-based wildfire smoke detection, enabling earlier warnings, reducing ecological and economic damage, and strengthening disaster prevention systems.

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